

Geometrical Inversion in the Acids Derived from the Coumarins.

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In a paper on the hydroxyquinolylacrylic acids and their derivatives (Dey and Seshadri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 189) it was pointed out that there existed a fundamental difference between the behaviour of the *trans* acids and of their esters under the action of heat. The former decomposed into the corresponding styrenes and carbon dioxide, whereas the latter eliminated alcohol to form the original pyrones. What was then considered to be an isolated phenomenon peculiar only to the hydroxyquinolylacrylic acids has since been discovered to be a property common to all members of the coumaric acid series.

It was considered to be of some importance to examine if there was any tendency on the part of any of the coumaric acids to go over into the coumarins when heated, and with this end in view the decomposition of *o*-coumaric acid and its nitro and methoxy derivatives was studied closely. No formation of the coumarins was detected and the styrenes were obtained exclusively.

In contrast with the action of heat, the effect of sunlight on the *trans* acids and their esters is found to be quite similar both being converted into the coumarins. The esters, however, underwent inversion more readily than the acids. The effect of substituents such as a methoxy group and a nitro group in the benzene ring has also been investigated. The latter markedly accelerates the transformation of both the acids and their esters, whereas the former produces just the opposite. Table I gives the percentage conversion of the acids and esters when exposed to bright sunshine in alcoholic solution for different intervals of time.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Time of exposure.	Product.	% Conversion.
<i>o</i> -Coumaric acid	24 hrs.	Coumarin	65
Methyl coumarate	"	"	87
Ethyl coumarate	"	"	74
4-Methoxycoumaric acid	"	7-Methoxycoumarin	51
Methyl 4-methoxycoumarate	"	"	55
Ethyl " "	"	"	55
5-Nitrocoumaric acid	12	6-Nitrocoumarin	99
Methyl 5-nitrocoumarate	"	"	100
Ethyl " "	"	"	99
<i>o</i> -Coumaric acid	6	Coumarin	48
Methyl coumarate	"	"	54
4-Methoxycoumaric acid	"	7-Methoxycoumarin	30
Methyl 4-methoxycoumarate	"	"	42
5-Nitrocoumaric acid	"	6-Nitrocoumarin	80
Methyl 5-nitrocoumarate	"	"	90

Table II gives the percentage conversion of the *trans* esters into the coumarins when heated. It will be noticed that the effects of the substituents are similar to those found in the photochemical inversion. The conditions of decomposition by heat are, however, not so easily controllable as in the case of light and it would not be correct to draw conclusions of a quantitative nature from these results.

TABLE II.

Ester decomposed.	Time of heating.	Product.	Yield.
Methyl coumarate	5 min.	Coumarin	45%
Ethyl coumarate	"	"	46
Methyl 4-methoxycoumarate	"	7-Methoxycoumarin	44
Ethyl " "	"	"	41
Methyl 5-nitrocoumarate	2 min.	6-Nitrocoumarin	76
Ethyl " "	"	"	73

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Coumaric acid was prepared from coumarin by the method of Dey and Row (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 561) as well as by that of Sen and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247), the former method gave a better yield of the pure acid (20 g. from 20 g. of coumarin), the latter method gave only 3 g. of the acid from 5 g. of coumarin. The yield was, however, raised to 4 g. by adopting the following modification :

The purified mercury complex was boiled with dilute alcohol (50 c.c., 50%) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) for a few minutes and filtered hot. A second extraction of the residue removed a further small quantity. The combined filtrate was boiled to drive off most of the alcohol and on cooling the solution, *o*-coumaric acid crystallised out.

The methyl and ethyl esters of the acid were prepared by two methods: (a) by boiling coumarin with a molecular equivalent of sodium alcoholate in absolute methyl or ethyl alcohol for 4 hours (Biilmann, *Annalen*, 1912, 388, 228) and, (b) by boiling coumaric acid with absolute alcohol containing 2% anhydrous hydrogen chloride for 6 hours (Biilmann, *ibid.*, p. 279). When alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride gas was employed for the esterification, ring-closure of the acid occurred giving rise to free coumarin. The methyl ester readily crystallised from benzene, m.p. 137°, yield by the first method 20 g. from 29.2 g. of coumarin, whereas by the second method it was 5 g. from 5 g. of the acid. The ethyl ester was easily obtained pure and crystalline by dissolving it in light petroleum in which it was very soluble and pouring the solution into a large volume of ligroin, m.p. 86°, yields were 15.9 g. from 29.2 g. of coumarin and 5 g. from 5 g. of coumaric acid.

5-Nitrocoumaric acid was obtained from 6-nitrocoumarin (Morgan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1233). The sodium sulphite method gave a rather poor yield of the acid (7 g. from 20 g. of nitrocoumarin). Modifications in which the nitrocoumarin was boiled for a shorter time with sodium sulphite or in which lower concentrations of potash were used, did not improve the yield. Though the use of mercuric acetate resulted in a better yield, the product obtained was rather impure and required several crystallisations. When mercuric oxide (Sen and Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*) was employed,

however, the process was quicker and the product was obtained purer and in better yield (4 g. from 5 g. of nitrocoumarin).

The methyl and ethyl esters of the acid could not be made direct from nitrocoumarin by using sodium alcoholate since the reagent attacked the nitro group also. It was, therefore, prepared by esterifying the acid with alcohol containing 2% dry hydrogen chloride. The methyl ester melted at 210° (Dey and Row, *loc. cit.*), yield 4.7 g. from 5 g. of the acid. The ethyl ester crystallised as colourless needles which slowly turned yellow on exposure to air, m.p. $170-72^{\circ}$, yield 3.5 g. from 5 g. of the acid. (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5$ N requires N, 5.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxycoumarin (Umbelliferone) (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 132) was prepared as follows. Equimolecular quantities of dry resorcinol and malic acid were intimately mixed and heated carefully on a wire-gauze with double their weight of concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.88). The mixture began to froth up in a few minutes with evolution of carbon dioxide and eventually solidified. Heating was continued until the solid just remelted and the reaction was then allowed to complete by itself. When the gas evolution ceased the mixture was again heated and the process was repeated till the liquid became suddenly clear and quite free from gas bubbles. After cooling, the melt was poured into five times its weight of ice-water and the solid was crystallised from methanol (charcoal) as colourless rhombic prisms, m.p. $223-24^{\circ}$, yield 4 g. from 13 g. of malic acid and 11 g. of resorcinol. (The success of the method was found to depend mainly on the regulation of the heating which should be stopped precisely at the moment the mixture becomes clear.)

7-Methoxycoumarin was obtained from umbelliferone by methylating with dimethyl sulphate in presence of aqueous alkali or in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in benzene.

Resorcinol (11 g.) dissolved in caustic soda (10% , 40 c.c.) was treated at $60-70^{\circ}$ as usual with dimethylsulphate (12-13 g.) and the mixture was finally heated on the boiling water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the oil taken up with ether, the ether distilled off and the oil distilled in steam. The distillate was extracted with ether and then with 10% aqueous caustic soda. The alkaline solution was acidified, extracted with ether, dried and distilled at $242-43^{\circ}$, yield 7.5 g.

The reaction of monomethylresorcinol with malic acid to produce umbelliferone methylether is more easily controlled and the yield is

almost theoretical. The crude product crystallised from methanol (charcoal) as colourless leaflets, m. p. 117-18°.

4-Methoxycoumaric acid was obtained from 7-methoxycoumarin (i) by boiling it with alcoholic potash (Barth and Harzig, *Monatsch.*, 1889, 10, 165) and (ii) by treatment with sodium sulphite and alkali, yield 2 g. from 5 g. of the coumarin. The esters of the acid were obtained by the same methods as were applied in the case of coumaric acid. The *methyl ester* crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 138°. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.7. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.5; H, 5.8 per cent). The *ethyl ester* crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 109°.

Decomposition of the o-coumaric acids by heat.—*o*-Coumaric acid was heated under conditions employed by Krause (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 369) for the preparation of *o*-vinylphenol. The distillate as well as the residue in the distilling flask were both examined for the presence of coumarin by dissolving them in ether, shaking the solution with 2% aqueous potash so as to remove vinylphenol and its polymers, drying the ether solution and evaporating it to dryness. No residue was left thereby showing that coumarin formation did not take place at all under these circumstances. The decompositions of the nitro- and methoxycoumaric acids were very vigorous and uncontrollable giving rise to brownish resinous residues having the odour of phenol; no definite compounds could be isolated.

Action of Heat on the Esters of the Coumaric Acids (trans).

Methyl coumarate (1 g.) was heated carefully for 5 minutes in a dry test tube over a small flame, the contents being stirred. The orange-red liquid turned into a mass of crystals on cooling. It was dissolved in ether, the undecomposed ester removed with 2% aqueous caustic soda and the ether removed. The colourless crystals were found to be identical with coumarin, m.p. 67°, yield 45%. The ethyl ester behaved similarly and produced coumarin in an yield of 46%.

Methyl and ethyl 4-methoxycoumarates produced 7-methoxycoumarin, m.p. 117-18°. (yield 44 and 41%). The *esters of 5-nitro-coumaric acid* underwent this change more readily and heating for 2 minutes was found to be sufficient. The product of decomposition was digested in the cold with 2% aqueous alkali, filtered and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 183-85° and was found to be

identical with 6-nitrocoumarin, yields 76% (from the methyl ester) and 73% (from the ethyl ester).

Action of Sunlight on the trans-Acids and their Esters.

o-Coumaric acid and its methyl ester were exposed to bright sunshine for 24 hours in silica tubes and were examined at intervals for m. p. and solubility in sodium carbonate and hydroxide respectively. No change was observed. A solution of 2 g. of the pure acid or the ester in 50 c.c. of ethyl alcohol was placed in a silica flask and exposed to bright sunshine for 24, 12 or 6 hours according to circumstances. The weather conditions were uniformly good.

After exposure, the alcohol was distilled off, the residue taken up in ether, the coumaric acid or its ester removed by 5% sodium bicarbonate (2% bicarbonate in the case of ester), washed with water and the coumaric acid dried over sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator for 24 hours and the ether removed, yield in case of *o*-coumaric acid 65% (after 24 hours) and 48% (after 6 hours). Methyl coumarate gave (87% after 24 hours and 54% after 6 hours) coumarin, whereas ethyl coumarate gave coumarin (74% after 24 hours).

4-Methoxycoumaric acid was treated just in the same way as coumaric acid. It yielded 0.92 g. of 7-methoxycoumarin after 24 hours' exposure (51%) and 0.60 g. after 6 hours (30%). The methyl ester gave 0.94 g. of methoxycoumarin after 24 hours (55%) and 0.72 g. after 6 hours (42%), whereas the ethyl ester gave 0.87 g. of methoxycoumarin (55%) after 24 hours' exposure.

5-Nitrocoumaric acid.—The original orange-red solution of the acid turned paler as the exposure proceeded and needle shaped yellow crystals of 6-nitrocoumarin began to separate. At the end of 6 or 12 hours' exposure (the conversion was found to be complete after 12 hours) the solvent was distilled off and the residue was digested with cold aqueous sodium bicarbonate in order to remove the unchanged acid, filtered, washed with water, dried in a desiccator and weighed. This purification was not necessary after 12 hours' exposure since the residue after removing alcohol was found to be pure nitrocoumarin showing no trace of the presence of the unchanged acid, yield of nitrocoumarin after 12 hours was 1.8 g. (99%) and after 6 hours' exposure 1.5 g. (80%).

The esters also underwent complete conversion after 12 hours' exposure ; the methyl ester gave 1.69 g. and the ethyl ester 1.59 g. of pure 6-nitrocoumarin. After 6 hours' exposure, however, the reaction was still incomplete ; the unchanged ester in the product was removed by digestion with cold 2% aqueous potash, filtered, washed with water, dried and weighed. The yield from the methyl ester was 1.5 g. (90% conversion).

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